

HORIZON 2020

Research and Innovation action

Grant Agreement No. 730965

ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:

**A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic**

**Deliverable 4.3. Definition of the ARICE Call for
proposals including Evaluation criteria and Submission
Guidelines**

Submission of Deliverable

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Deliverable No. 4.3.

Definition of the ARICE Call for proposals including Evaluation Criteria and Submission Guidelines

Abstract

ARICE opened its first call for ship time proposals on the 12th of April 2018 and it will remain open till the 5th of July 2018. The call was widely distributed by email to project partners, representatives of international polar programmes and projects, the European Polar Board and researchers for information and further distribution.

The call package information consists on the following five documents, which are available for download in the section Apply for Ship Time from the ARICE Website

<https://arice.eu/documents> until call closure, and are included in this deliverable:

- 1) General information for applicantsPage 5
- 2) Online submission guidelines.....Page 17
- 3) Proposal templatePage 30
- 4) CV TemplatePage 36
- 5) Evaluation Criteria.....Page 37

The screenshot shows the ARICE website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, About, News, Outreach, Apply for Ship Time, and Intranet. Below this, the page title is 'Call Documents and Templates'. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column contains a sidebar with links to various documents: General Information, Eligibility Criteria, General Funding, Access Conditions and Limitations, Specific Terms for Access to RV Sikuliaq, Specific Terms for Access to COGS Amundsen, Specific Terms for Access to PRV Polarstern, ARICE Data Policy, Evaluation Process, Evaluation Criteria, Call Documents and Templates, and Contact. The right column is titled 'Call Documents and Templates' and contains the text 'The documents are available for download in PDF format:' followed by a list of links: ARICE2018 - General Information for Applicants, ARICE2018 – PART B -Proposal Template, ARICE2018 – Online Submission Guidelines, ARICE2018 – Proposal Evaluation and Evaluation Criteria, CV Template, OSPAR Code of Conduct for Responsible Marine Research, and MOSAIC distribution of legs. At the bottom of the page, there is a footer with social media icons, a navigation menu, and the text 'Designed & hosted by Arctic Portal'.

ARICE2018

CALL FOR SHIP-TIME

PROPOSALS

GENERAL INFORMATION FOR

APPLICANTS

Project website:

www.arice.eu

Version 10.04.2018

Introduction

On the first of January 2018, a consortium of 15 partners (13 EU partners together with USA and Canada) launched the European project **ARICE “Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium: A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research in the Arctic”**, funded by the European Commission as a “Research and Innovation Action” on the topic “Integrating Activities for Starting Communities”.

ARICE’s overall aim is to provide Europe with better capacities for marine-based research in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean with the existing polar fleet.

In this context, **ARICE will provide researchers with transnational access to a set of six research icebreakers:**

- PRV Polarstern, Germany
- IB Oden, Sweden
- RV Kronprins Haakon, Norway
- RRS Sir David Attenborough, United Kingdom
- CCGS Amundsen, Canada
- RV Sikuliaq, United States of America

ARICE will open two calls for ship-time proposals, one in spring 2018, and a second one early in 2019:

ARICE CALL 2018 giving access to PRV Polarstern, CCGS Amundsen, and RV Sikuliaq, and

ARICE CALL 2019 giving access to IB Oden, RV Kronprins Haakon and RRS Sir David Attenborough.

We are now inviting you to submit ship-time proposals requesting access to PRV Polarstern, CCGS Amundsen and RV Sikuliaq in the Arctic Ocean to carry out ship-based research activities within any field of marine science (restrictions may apply, check further information below).

This call will remain open till the 5th of July 2018 3pm CEST.

The central aim of ARICE is to provide access to the Arctic Research Icebreakers to EU and non-EU researchers and their partners including industry. Access priority will be granted **based on scientific excellence. Researchers of all career stages are encouraged to apply.**

ARICE funded ship-time forms part of longer cruises (up to 2 months long) with different working groups embarked (nationally or internationally funded). This will maximize the operational days in the working areas but will require that scientific parties remain on board for a longer time.

For more information on ARICE calls for proposals and on the research icebreaker capabilities, schedule and geographic areas offered visit the vessel descriptions at www.arice.eu

Proposals must be submitted using the proposal submission portal <https://secure.pt-dlr.de/ptoutline/app/arice2018>

[Check carefully if you fulfil the eligibility criteria before submitting your application.](#)

[Instructions on how to draft the proposal can be found in the document ARICE2018 PART B – Proposal Template.](#)

[Detailed instructions to submit your proposal online can be found in the document **ARICE2018 Online Submission Guidelines**.](#)

[Documents and templates are available at https://arice.eu/documents](https://arice.eu/documents)

Deadline

Proposals must be received online via the [online proposal submission website](#) by

Thursday 5th of July 2018, 15:00 HOURS (CEST)

The proposal submission website will not be accessible after this date. Please allow enough time to upload your proposal to avoid the call closure rush.

Access Units

ARICE will fund access “free of charge”, up to 7 days of ship time for teams of 6 to 10 researchers (see specific vessel description), to successful applicants on board each one of the six ARICE Research Icebreakers in the Arctic Ocean. **This call ARICE2018 offers time to three of the six ARICE research icebreakers: PRV Polarstern, CCGS Amundsen and RV Sikuliaq.**

Because of the limited funding available through ARICE, the proponents are encouraged to adjust their research plans to the number of days offered per research icebreaker in order to benefit from access free of charge. Additional days can be chartered by successful applicants if agreed with the ARICE research icebreakers operators.

APPLICATIONS TO POLARSTERN IN THE FRAME OF the MOSAiC EXPEDITION

Due to the special configuration of MOSAiC, the funding provided by ARICE is not counted as days of working time, but limited to a maximum participation of persons per leg, in multiple combinations, depending on leg duration:

- Up to 5- 6 participants / 1 leg (single project)
- Up to 2 participants in 3 legs (in one or multiple projects)
- 1 participant / 4-5 legs (in one or multiple projects)

Applications are welcome for a minimum of 1 person/leg.

Potential applicants are warned that their work will span the full leg duration and that change of personnel can only occur between MOSAiC legs.

Access Mode

Access to any Research Icebreaker in ARICE will be regulated according to the **Excellence-driven access mode**. This mode of access is dependent on the scientific excellence, originality, quality and technical and ethical feasibility of an application evaluated through peer review conducted by external experts.

Eligibility criteria

Trans-national access will be provided to selected ‘user-groups’, i.e. teams of one or more researchers (users) led by a ‘user group leader’. Proposals for access to ARICE Research Icebreakers will be accepted for evaluation if they meet all of the following **six strict criteria**:

- 1. (ONLY APPLICATIONS TO POLARSTERN)** Proposals must include an **Endorsement Letter** from MOSAiC: Potential participants are encouraged to start this endorsement process as early as possible; the endorsement process is expected to take 3 weeks from the submission of the request for endorsement until endorsement is confirmed. More information under: <http://www.mosaic-expedition.org/participation.html>
- 2. Affiliation (1):** The user group leader and the majority of the users must work in a country other than the country the requested infrastructure is based. For example, a user group leader (or Principal Investigator) working at a German institution is entitled to apply for ship-time in the frame of ARICE on all of the listed ARICE vessels except the PRV Polarstern, as PRV Polarstern belongs to a German institution. This requirement ensures that access to RV and equipment is transnational.
- 3. Affiliation (2):** More than 50% of the users within each user group and embarked team must work in an institution established in a EU or associated country¹. Access for user groups with a majority of users not working in a EU or H2020 associated country is limited to 20% of the total amount of access provided under the grant, and thus access to these user groups may be rejected to keep within the quota.
- 4. International cooperation:** proposals must involve at least three partners from three different countries. This requirement supports the spirit of international cooperation and opens opportunities to newcomers. Larger partnerships are encouraged for the proposals partnerships, for the embarked scientific party and as well for the remote participation of partners for data treatment and exploitation.
- 5. Training:** Proposals must include an advanced training or educational programme for early career scientists or technicians.
- 6. Dissemination:** Only user groups that are entitled to and willing to disseminate the knowledge they will generate under the project are eligible to benefit from access free of charge to the infrastructures under the ARICE flag, unless the users are working for Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). User groups must agree to comply with the ARICE data policy.

The non-fulfilment of any of the previous criteria implies the non-acceptance of the proposal for further evaluation.

¹ Legal entities from Associated Countries can participate under the same conditions as legal entities from the Member States. As of 01 January 2017, the following countries are associated to Horizon 2020: Iceland, Norway, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Turkey, Israel, Moldova, Switzerland, Faroe Islands, Ukraine, Tunisia, Georgia, Armenia.

Terms and Conditions

general Funding and access conditions

1. Funding is provided for accessing the ARICE Research Icebreakers. Ship-time may be awarded in a single leg or multiple legs, depending on the recommendations of the ARICE Scientific Liaison Panel and Logistic Liaison Panel and subject to the formal approval of the ARICE Steering Board.
2. European funding will cover the use of the vessel (with berth limitation), full crew, fuel, victuals and other standard operating costs. Travel expenses for the embarked team and transport of equipment will be covered up to a maximum amount of 45.000€.
3. The access will include the logistical, technological and scientific support, and the specific training that is usually provided to external researchers using the infrastructure.
4. Grantees will not invoice the ARICE Consortium or respective vessel operator for any additional or third-party costs, such as salary costs, equipment manufacture, repair and rental of equipment, consumables, sub-contracting and assistance, publication costs and overheads.
5. The available ship-time funded by ARICE might be extended providing sufficient complementary funding by the applicant for additional ship-time. The leveraging of funds from other sources for a portion of the total amount of ship-time applied for is encouraged and should be clearly stated in the application. However, please be aware, that cross funding from other EU projects is not permitted. A cruise or work funded already by another EU project cannot be proposed to ARICE funding.
6. ARICE funded ship-time forms part of longer cruises (up to 2 months long) with different working groups embarked.
7. The PI or a designated cruise leader of a proposal must have the appropriate scientific/technical expertise to conduct on board research surveys.
8. If the number of funded days is reduced by the ARICE Consortium for any reason or if the vessels are prevented from working (e.g. by poor weather or technical difficulties) no form of compensation shall be payable in respect of any time lost. Please note that cruise schedules could change during the year.
9. Vessel users should note that installation and operation of any equipment that they bring on board the vessels is done so at their own risk. Users must indemnify the respective vessel operator against loss or damage to user-owned equipment whilst it is carried on board or deployed from the vessel. Further details will be provided during the negotiation phase.
10. A contract will be signed between the PIs institution, the ARICE Consortium and the beneficiary giving access to its infrastructure detailing laying out terms and conditions of access, including the support granted, reporting, liability, applicable safety/security regulations and modalities of payment of travel and subsistence costs of the scientific party.

Access limitation

Access should be provided in order to conduct research, to undertake experimental development, to provide education and training and to deliver services. Access should be granted with an exclusive focus on civil applications and comply with ethical principles. Access to the ARICE Research Icebreakers may be limited, amongst others, by the following: national security and defence, privacy and confidentiality, commercial sensitivity and intellectual property rights and ethical considerations in accordance with applicable laws and regulations.

Specific Terms for ACCESS TO RV Sikuliaq

RV Sikuliaq operational areas: Proposals to RV Sikuliaq will be accepted to perform research in the following geographic regions: **Bering, Chukchi, and Beaufort Seas.**

Proposals selected for funding on board the RV Sikuliaq will be scheduled through the University-National Oceanographic Laboratory System (UNOLS) Ship Time Request & Scheduling System https://strs.unols.org/Public/diu_login.aspx

Contact the operator of RV Sikuliaq Doug Baird at e-mail address: ddbaird2@alaska.edu

Specific Terms for ACCESS TO CCGS AMUNDSEN

CCGS Amundsen operational areas: Proposals to CCGS Amundsen will be accepted to perform multidisciplinary oceanographic studies in the following geographic regions (following the preliminary schedule for CCGS Amundsen):

2019 Late May to early July: Northern Labrador Sea, Southern Baffin Bay

2020 August to December: Southern and Northern Baffin Bay, North Water Polynya/Nares Strait, Lancaster Sound

2021 July to November: Southern and Northern Baffin Bay, Baffin Bay, Northwest Passage, Southeastern Beaufort Sea

Proposals selected for funding on board the CCGS Amundsen will be scheduled through the Amundsen ship-time application.

Applicants are welcomed to discuss the initial feasibility of their work while they prepare their application with the operator of CCGS Amundsen, Amundsen Science at info@as.ulaval.ca

Specific Terms FOR ACCESS TO POLARSTERN

The access to PRV Polarstern is offered in the frame of the **Multidisciplinary Drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate (MOSAiC) Expedition**, the first year-round expedition into the central Arctic exploring the Arctic climate system.

NOTE: Proposals submitted to ARICE for PRV Polarstern will require a **Confirmation of Endorsement from MOSAiC** (see further below), a process which is encouraged to be started by potential applicants as soon as possible, as the endorsement process is expected to take 3 weeks from the submission of the request for endorsement until endorsement is confirmed.

MOSAiC will investigate processes in the atmosphere, sea ice and snow, ocean, bio-geochemistry and ecosystem for a period of one year, including the winter season. The results of MOSAiC will contribute to enhance the understanding of the regional and global consequences of Arctic climate change and sea-ice loss, and improve weather and climate predictions.

MOSAiC welcomes broad participation from the research community and fosters collaboration and coordination to achieve significant advances in our understanding of central Arctic, coupled-system processes. In particular, ARICE invites the research community to contribute to ensure a year around observation of specific measurements or to fill specific research gaps.

Potential applications for Transnational Access on board PRV Polarstern in the frame of MOSAiC must comply with:

- a) The **ARICE access regulations specific to PRV Polarstern in the frame of MOSAiC**.
- b) the MOSAiC participation strategy (<http://www.mosaic-expedition.org/participation.html>), which includes contacting the appropriate members of the MOSAiC Project Board and submitting a completed **MOSAiC endorsement template**([Link](#)) to the MOSAiC Coordination Office (Dr. Anja Sommerfeld: Anja.Sommerfeld@awi.de). Successful applicants will thereafter receive a **Confirmation of Endorsement** letter.

Potential applicants should therefore contact the MOSAiC team coordinators (<http://www.mosaic-expedition.org/organisation.html>) as soon as possible to ensure that their project can be embedded in MOSAiC. The MOSAiC Project Board will evaluate the endorsement proposal, possibly consulting with the applicant for more information, and make a decision within 3 weeks. This endorsement letter must be submitted to ARICE together with the ship time proposal (PART B, in pdf). **ARICE will automatically reject proposals for PRV Polarstern lacking the endorsement from MOSAiC.**

Additionally, **proposals funded through ARICE must align with the following research topics from the MOSAiC interdisciplinary initiative:**

Atmosphere

- Continuous in-situ profiling of the vertical dynamic, thermodynamic and aerosols/cloud microphysical properties by means of small instruments operated on tethered balloons, especially in conjunction with ship-based remote sensing, are essential for understanding surface energy forcing.

Sea ice

- Snow pack evolution and properties, including impurities and links to aerosols
- Snow and sea ice (horizontal and thickness) distributions on the aggregate scale.

- Seasonal characteristics of snow and sea ice derived from merging multiple (autonomous) platforms in the MOSAiC distributed network.
- Bio-physical linkages in different seasons, including new methods of habitat descriptions and analysis.

Ocean

- Continuous time/depth sampling to map distribution of oceanic vertical fluxes and turbulent structure, and their relation to submesoscale dynamics.
- Vertical structure of turbulent structure in the upper 100 m, up to the ice undersurface, during late freeze-up and early melt conditions.
- Interface and equip one IAOOS buoy with microstructure sensors, to facilitate internal data processing to relay reduced mixing parameters continuously through Iridium.
- Deploy an uprising vertical microstructure profiler with high quality dissipation measurements in the upper 100 m, up to the ice-water interface.

Ecosystem:

- Sea-ice carbonate chemistry.
- Bacterial production.

Bio-Geochemistry:

- The enrichment of the natural carbon export proxy ^{234}Th in sea-ice in winter. ^{234}Th is known to be enriched in sea-ice sometimes, but the actual process and how it affects C-export estimates is not well understood. This would add another science aspect to MOSAiC, link to the biological work and attract candidates who would be able to run ^7Be and ^{222}Rn , which is already implemented but not covered for all cruise legs. We can provide the analytical facilities for the ship as part of our container.

Technical information on ARICE research icebreakers

In preparation of their respective proposal, applicants are advised to consult the ARICE research vessel information websites on the technical capabilities, availability of scientific equipment of the research icebreaker they intend to apply for. If more detailed information is required, applicants should contact the respective research icebreaker operator, or the ARICE Evaluation Office at info@arice.eu and their request will be forwarded to the vessel operator.

Application procedure

Proposal submission involves three steps, as outlined below. Proposals have to be submitted online via the [online proposal submission website](#):

- **Step 1:** Register on the proposal submission website and retrieve a password for further access. Please note, that your password will only be displayed once and you should carefully remember it.
- **Step 2:** Prepare and submit your proposal, including all relevant information. This step consists of two main parts:
 - **Part A:** General information about the proposal, applicants (PI and user group) and technical information regarding the intended research cruise. This section has to be completed online.
 - **Part B:** Scientific description of the project. This part needs to be uploaded at the end of the online application process. **Please note that you are only permitted to upload one document.** This document must:
 - **be an unprotected pdf file**
 - **not exceed 4MB in size**
 - **Not exceed 14 pages**, excluding CVs (it is mandatory to use the dedicated [CV template](#)) and MOSAiC Endorsement Letter (if applicable), **but including all other appendices**. A font size of Times New Roman 12pt must be used with 14 pt spacing.
- **Step 3:** On the finalization of the proposal submission the system will automatically generate a **Proposal Summary Sheet** of the proposal submitted as a confirmation of a successful submission. Applicants should download a copy of this document. Proponents are able to preview the Proposal Summary Sheet whilst preparing their application following the Proposal Summary Sheet Preview link in the “Finalization” menu of the submission website.

In preparation of **Part B** applicants should follow the proposal structure as indicated in the document [ARICE2018 PART B Proposal Template](#). The evaluation of proposals will be based upon the information provided in the completed application form, which should be correct, sufficient and adequate for this purpose, taking into consideration the outlined **evaluation criteria** (see further below).

Freedom of Information & Data protection

Personal information supplied to the ARICE Consortium will be stored by electronic means (e.g. database) for use only in connection with the handling of proposals. All personal data supplied to the ARICE Consortium shall be processed in accordance with the Belgium Data Protection Act of 1992, as modified by the law of December 11, 1998 implementing Directive 95/46/EC entering into force in 2001, on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. You have the right to access and update the personal information about you and to ask for such information to be deleted.

All data processing activities, commencing after 25th of May 2018, will comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (replacing the EC Directive 95/46).

All applicants who wish to query the outcome of their application and seek for clarification may contact the ARICE Evaluation Office at info@arice.eu

Reporting

Following completion of a funded cruise **the PI must submit a Cruise Report (in English) to the ARICE Evaluation Office**. This report must be submitted in pdf at info@arice.eu, within two months after completion of the cruise and is designed to report on the science carried out during the cruise. It must explicitly refer to and comment on the fulfilment of the points of the work plan outlined in the proposal. **A cruise report template will be provided prior to cruise commencement**. The ARICE Scientific Liaison Panel may request further information/clarifications (or re-submission of the report) within a reasonable time-frame.

ARICE Data policy

ARICE aims at its research data to be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). Data management in ARICE is coordinated with relevant Arctic and oceanographic data management systems and adopts the Arctic Data Committee standards. The Arctic Data Committee can be visited at <https://arcticdc.org/>

All data generated under ARICE funding is accessible to the user group who collected the data. The Principal Investigator of an ARICE cruise must submit the data generated together with sufficient metadata to the respective IODE National Oceanographic Data Centre (NODCs)² within two months after cruise completion. The NODC will then make sure that the data sets are quality controlled, archived in the NODCs and linked to the metadata of the respective cruise. Datasets will also be integrated into the ARICE Data Management System, the ARICE project's database and disseminated in an interoperable open format through the 3D Icebreaker outreach tool. Access to the datasets, apart from metadata, can be restricted to the scientific party and its designated partners for a period of 1 to 3 years after the cruise takes place (depending on specific RV procedures). Requests of external users for data access during this time will be forwarded to the data originators for their decision.

Acknowledgements

All results/publications/presentations/publicity arising from a ARICE funded cruise should carry an **acknowledgment of the funding source as well as to the research vessel utilized, referring to support given by H2020 under ARICE Grant Agreement no. 730965**. Logos for presentations can be found on the [Project Website](#).

A copy of every publication arising from ARICE must be **sent to the ARICE Evaluation Office** for the project records.

² A list containing information on all IODE National Oceanographic Data Centres (NODCs) - as designated by the Government of these Member States - as well as IODE Associate Data Units ADUs) can be found here: https://www.iode.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=61&Itemid=100057 This page is updated annually or when the Secretariat receives information from Member States.

Contact Details

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ARICE2018

CALL FOR SHIP-TIME PROPOSALS

ONLINE SUBMISSION GUIDELINES

Project website:

www.arice.eu

Version 10.04.2018

ONLINE SUBMISSION GUIDELINES

The following pages offer a step-by-step guideline of the proposal submission process. You can use this as a checklist to make sure you have all the information needed in order to fill in the form. The different screenshots displayed in this document will guide you through the whole submission process.

Proposals must be submitted exclusively in electronic form via the [online proposal submission website](#).

The proposal submission involves three steps, as outlined below:

- **Step 1:** Registration on the proposal submission website and retrieval of a password for further access.
- **Step 2:** Preparation of your proposal, including all relevant information. This step consists of two main parts:

Part A: General information about the proposal, applicants (PI and scientific party) and technical information regarding the intended research cruise.

Part B: Scientific description of the project, which must be uploaded at the end of the online application process. In preparation of **Part B** applicants should follow the proposal structure as indicated in the [ARICE2018 Ship-time Application Guidelines](#).

- **Step 3:** Finalization and submission

On the finalization of the proposal submission, applicants will receive an automatically generated Proposal Summary Sheet of the proposal submitted, as a confirmation of a successful submission. You are able to preview this Proposal Summary Sheet at any time whilst preparing your application following the Proposal Summary Sheet Preview link in the “Finalization” menu of the submission website.

CLOSING DATE

Proposals must be received online via the [online proposal submission website](#) by

Thursday 5^h of July 2018, 15:00 HOURS (CEST)

The proposal submission website will no longer be accessible after this date. Please allow enough time to upload your proposal to avoid the call closure rush.

Step 1 – Login page

The Login page is the default page of the online proposal submission website you will be directed to. In order to be able to use the proposal submission system you have to register following the “Sign up” tab.

The image shows a web browser window displaying the PT-Outline login page. The browser's address bar shows the URL 'https://secure.pt-dlr.de/ptoutline/app/arice2018'. The page features the PT-Outline logo at the top left and two buttons for 'Site notice' and 'Support' at the top right. The main content area is titled 'ARICE2018' and includes the text 'ARCTIC RESEARCH ICEBREAKER CONSORTIUM - Call ARICE2018' and a link to 'www.arice.eu'. Below this is a login form with tabs for 'Login', 'Sign up', and 'Recover password'. The 'Login' tab is active, showing fields for 'E-Mail:' and 'Password', a 'Login' button, and a link for 'Forgot your password?'. At the bottom right, there is a copyright notice for 'DLR Projektträger'.

After providing your email address on the Registration page and clicking the button “Sign up” you will automatically receive an email containing a link to your password. **Please note, that your password will only be displayed once and you should carefully remember it.** Your email address becomes your username.

In case you forget your password, you can recover it by clicking the tab “Recover password”.

When you have secured the password you can click on “Activate Access”, which gives immediate access to the ARICE Login page above. After completion of this step you are able to login to the system at any time before the deadline, which will enable you to alter the submission (the system will save the data submitted) and to return, when convenient, to finalise the submission before the deadline.

In case you forget your password you can order a new one by clicking the tab “Recover password”. The new password will be send to your email account. **When using the new password data will not be lost.**

Please note, that for security reasons the system will automatically disconnect people after 120 minutes of inactivity. Therefore, please save your data regularly.

Step 2 - Overview

This is the Overview page displayed once you have logged in. You are able to reach this page at any stage during the submission process through clicking on the “Overview” field.

On the left hand side you find the links to the different menus of **Part A** and **Part B** of the proposal submission procedure, along with the finalization menu.

The screenshot shows the PT-Outline web application interface. The browser address bar indicates the URL: <https://secure.pt-dlr.de/ptoutline/app/forms/edit/>. The page title is "PT-Outline".

Navigation Menu (Left Side):

- forms (ARICE-349-004)
 - Overview**
 - I General Information
 - II Principal Investigator
 - III Project Partners
 - IV Project description
 - V Final Check and Submission
- Call details
 - Call acronym: ARICE2018
 - Call deadline: 05-07-2018 15:00 CEST
 - ARICE Evaluation Office**
Tina Swierczynski
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+49 331 288-2118
info@arice.eu
http://www.arice.eu

Main Content Area (Overview):

Overview

The five menu items on the left (General Information, Principal Investigator, Project Partners, Project description, Final Check and Submission) will guide you through the process of preparing and submitting your proposal. In order to fill in the different forms, please click on each of the menu items. Proposals are stored password protected and can be saved and edited at a later stage until the final submission. However, to save a site, mandatory fields on this respective site have to be filled in. Once the proposal is bindingly submitted by clicking on the 'Submit now' button on the last menu item NO FURTHER CHANGES can be made to your proposal.

Proposals must be submitted exclusively using this online tool. Proposals submitted via E-mail, fax, paper copy will not be considered.

Only the Principal investigator of a project consortium should register, enter the name and contact data of the other consortium partners, edit and save the electronic forms, upload the proposal and finally submit on behalf of the project consortium. Other consortium partners should not submit a separate proposal.

The proposal is stored password-protected. Connection to the server is SSL-encoded and data safety and protection of confidence are guaranteed.

Application Procedure

PART A:
General and technical information on the project, including applicants information (Project Coordinator and Project Partners). Please complete this part by inserting project-specific information into the designated fields under the links on the left hand side.

PART B:
Scientific and financial description of the project. This part must be uploaded as PDF file under "Project description" at the end of the application process. Please note that you are only permitted to upload one document. This document must:

- Be an unprotected file.
- Not exceed 4MB in size.
- Not exceed 14 pages. CVs (using the dedicated CV template) and MOSAiC Endorsement Letter (if applying to PRV Polarstern) will not count towards the page limit, but any other appendix yes. A font size of Times New Roman 12pt should be used with 14pt spacing.

SUBMIT:
Please **check** all entries and complete the **binding submission** of the proposal by clicking on the 'Submit now' button.

You can work separately in the different menus. After completion of each form you must save the content so you can open the filled-in form later. If you do not save the data, data will be lost. Data can be changed and adapted until the moment you finally submit the proposal.

Fields marked with an orange asterisk are mandatory. If you leave any of those fields empty, a red warning box will appear on top of any empty field when saving the data.

Step 2 – Part A: (I) General and logistical project information

In the **General Information** menu, you must include information on the project, logistics and budget.

The screenshot shows the PT-Outline web application interface. The browser address bar displays 'Sicher | https://secure.pt-dlr.de/ptoutline/app/forms/edit/'. The page title is 'PT-Outline'. A sidebar on the left contains a navigation menu with the following items: Overview, **I General Information**, II Principal Investigator, III Project Partners, IV Project description, and V Final Check and Submission. Below the menu is contact information for the ARICE Evaluation Office.

The main content area is divided into sections:

- General Information:** Includes fields for Project title, Acronym (max. 10 characters), Project outline (max. 2000 characters), and Main scientific discipline(s).
- Agreement:** A radio button selection for 'Yes' or 'No' regarding the publication of abstract and keywords.
- Logistics Information:** Includes fields for ARICE Research Icebreaker, Working Area, Working days, Number of cruise participants, Which Exclusive Economic Zone(s) will be affected?, When should the cruise take place?, Ships onboard equipment needed, Ships mobile equipment needed, and Own equipment provided.
- Financial Information:** Includes fields for Total travel budget and Total shipment budget.

A 'Save' button is located at the bottom of the form. A note at the bottom states: 'N.B.: Please note the given limits for reimbursement on the respective vessel profile page. Detailed financial figures have to be provided in Part B section 7.'

ARICE will publish the abstract and keywords of your proposal, if selected, as well as the names of the different proposers on the public website. You can inform us by selecting “YES” or “NO” whether you agree, or not, to display this information.

Select the ARICE Research Icebreaker you would like to apply for: PRV Polarstern (in the frame of the MOSAiC Expedition), CCGS Amundsen and RV Sikuliaq. Read carefully the conditions for accessing each of the ARICE Icebreakers before applying.

The Financial Information (travel and shipment budget estimation) must correspond with the calculation made in PART B of the proposal.

You must click on the “Save” button to save your data and to continue with the next section.

Step 2 – Part A: (II) Principal Investigator

The screenshot displays the PT-Outline web application interface. The main content area is titled "II Principal Investigator" and contains a form for entering contact details. The form includes the following fields and sections:

- Title ***: A dropdown menu with "Please choose..." selected.
- Family name ***: A text input field with "characters left: 255".
- First name ***: A text input field.
- Gender**: Radio buttons for "Male" and "Female".
- Institution name ***: A text input field with "characters left: 255".
- Type of organization ***: A dropdown menu with "Please choose..." selected.
- Department/Research Group**: A text input field with "characters left: 255".
- Address ***: A text input field with "characters left: 150".
- Postal code ***: A text input field with "characters left: 150".
- City ***: A text input field with "characters left: 150".
- Country ***: A dropdown menu with "Please choose..." selected.
- E-Mail ***: A text input field with "characters left: 255".
- Telephone number ***: A text input field with "characters left: 100".
- Declaration ***: A section containing a declaration statement and a "Yes, I agree" checkbox.

The "Save" button is located at the bottom of the form.

The **Principal Investigator** menu includes contact information and a Declaration statement.

The PI must agree with the declaration stated on this page, see Appendix I at the end of this document for further information. Otherwise you will not be able to continue with the submission process!

You must click on the “Save” button to save your data and to continue with the next section.

In order to meet the **eligibility criteria of ARICE**, the PI must be based at a different country than the Research Icebreaker he/she is applying to.

Step 2 – Part A: (III) Project partner(s)

The information required in the menu **Project Partner(s)** is essentially the same as for the principal investigator:

The screenshot shows the PT-Outline web application interface. The browser address bar indicates the URL: https://secure.pt-dlr.de/ptoutline/app/forms/edit_multiform/. The page title is "PT-Outline".

On the left sidebar, there is a menu for "forms (ARICE-349-004)" with the following items:

- Overview
- I General Information
- II Principal Investigator
- III Project Partners** (highlighted with a red circle)
- IV Project description
- V Final Check and Submission

Below the menu, there is a "Call details" section with the following information:

- Call acronym: ARICE2018
- Call deadline: 05-07-2018 15:00 CEST
- ARICE Evaluation Office: Tina Swierczynski, Alfred Wegener Institut, +49 331 289-2118, info@arice.eu, http://www.arice.eu

The main content area displays the "III Project Partners" form. The form includes the following fields and sections:

- Title ***: A dropdown menu with "Please choose..." selected.
- Family name ***: A text input field with "characters left: 255".
- First name ***: A text input field.
- Gender ***: Radio buttons for "Male" and "Female".
- Institution name ***: A text input field with "characters left: 255".
- Type of organization ***: A dropdown menu with "Please choose..." selected.
- Department/Research Group**: A text input field with "characters left: 255".
- Address ***: A text input field with "characters left: 150".
- Postal code ***: A text input field with "characters left: 150".
- City ***: A text input field with "characters left: 150".
- Country ***: A dropdown menu with "Please choose..." selected.
- E-Mail ***: A text input field with "characters left: 255".
- Telephone number ***: A text input field with "characters left: 100".
- Declaration *** (highlighted with a red circle): A section containing a declaration text and a "Yes, I agree" checkbox.

At the bottom of the form, there is a "Save" button.

Please Note:

The Project Partner(s) must agree with the declaration stated on this page in order to continue with the submission process.

If information on existing project partners needs to be updated or a project partner needs to be deleted, you are able to do this following the respective icons behind a project partner.

You must click on the “Save” button to save your data and to continue with the next section.

You can add other project partners after saving the information. An additional button will appear.

The screenshot shows the PT-Outline web application interface. The browser address bar indicates the URL: https://secure.pt-dlr.de/ptoutline/app/forms/edit_multiform/349/3089/33660/4. The page title is "PT-Outline". The sidebar on the left contains a navigation menu with options: Overview, I General Information, II Principal Investigator, III Project Partners (highlighted), IV Project description, and V Final Check and Submission. Below the sidebar, there is a "Call details" section with information about the ARICE Evaluation Office. The main content area features a "Successfully saved" message at the top. Below this, there is a section titled "III Project Partners" with a list of existing partners, including "Luisa Example" with a "Delete form" button. A red circle highlights the "add project partner" button. Below the list, there is a form for adding a new partner, with fields for Title, Family name, First name, Gender, and Institution name. The form includes instructions and a "SAVE" button at the bottom.

Important note: In order to meet the eligibility criteria of the ARICE2018 call, the partnership must be composed of a minimum of three applicants (1 PI and 2 partners) all based at different countries. International PIs and Partners are welcome. **See full eligibility criteria at [ARICE2018 General Information for Applicants](#)**

Step 2 – Part B: (IV) Scientific project description

With this step you access PART B of the proposal submission and you will need to have the document ready for uploading. The document must be prepared according to the specifications described in the [ARICE2018 Ship-time application guidelines](#).

Please allow the system sufficient time to complete the upload. You will get a confirmation screen upon a successful upload and you will see the uploaded pdf of your project description appearing at the top of the page.

Important note: You are able to upload a modified version of your scientific project description anytime until the deadline. **However, no modifications are possible after you have submitted your final proposal as described in the next step.**

Step 3 – Finalization (V)

On this page you are able to finalize the submission of your proposal:

At any time whilst preparing your application you are able to **preview a Proposal Summary Sheet** supplied as a pdf-file following the Proposal Summary Sheet Preview link. In the right upper corner on each page of the Proposal Summary Sheet an automatically generated project-ID is displayed. This ID should be used in any correspondence with the ARICE Evaluation Office.

Modification of information: Before the submission is finalised all data in all forms can be modified. Just go to the relevant page and input your edits. As soon as the page has been saved the information Proposal Summary Sheet will change as well.

Important note: If you click on the “Submit NOW” button, your submission is completed and you will not be able to come back to your proposal (even with your password). **Modifications to the proposal are not possible any more after this stage.**

After having finally submitted a proposal the PI will receive an automatically generated email, as a **confirmation of a successful submission.**

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL https://secure.pt-dlr.de/ptoutline/app/forms/submit_outline/. The page title is "PT-Outline". The main content area is titled "V Final Check and Submission".

Navigation Menu:

- Overview
- I General Information
- II Principal Investigator
- III Project Partners
- IV Project description
- V Final Check and Submission**

Call details:

Call acronym
ARICE2018

Call deadline
05-07-2018 15:00 CEST

ARICE Evaluation Office
Tina Swierczynski
Alfred Wegener Institut
+49 331 288-2118
info@arice.eu
http://www.arice.eu

V Final Check and Submission

Proposal Summary Sheet preview

Finalization
To check for necessary revisions or amendments, you can prepare a preview of the data entered at anytime until the final deadline.

Binding Submission
After the following binding submission NO FURTHER CHANGES can be made.
Please submit your proposal and follow the instructions displayed to you afterwards. Deadline for submission is 05th of July 2018 15:00 CEST. The electronic submission system will be closed afterwards.

Verify Submission

Contact Details

ARICE Project Manager

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APPENDIX I

OSPAR Code of Conduct for Responsible Marine Research in the Deep Seas and High Seas of the OSPAR Maritime Area

Version: 7-Mar-2008

Background

1. This code of conduct is based on the InterRidge Statement of Commitment to Responsible Research Practices at Deep-Sea Hydrothermal Vents, and an unofficial translation of the German Senatskommission für Ozeanographie / German Marine Consortium KDM, Commitment to Responsible Marine Research. It has been developed within the work programme of the OSDPAR Biodiversity Committee by an intersessional correspondence group on marine protected areas working in consultation with a number of deep sea scientists and experts. It is currently being circulated to European scientific bodies for further comment.
2. The OSPAR Maritime Area includes large areas of deep and high sea.³ These are recognised as containing ecosystems that may have a lower resilience than shallower nearshore areas, including several species and habitats that can be vulnerable to human disturbances.
3. The OSPAR Commission has adopted, and keeps under review, an Initial OSPAR List of Threatened and/or Declining Species and Habitats (OSPAR agreement 2004/6) to guide the setting priorities for its further work on the conservation and protection of marine biodiversity. The species and habitats on this list, especially those occurring in high / deep sea areas, are vulnerable to different actual or potential human activities, including marine scientific research.
4. OSPAR acknowledges the provisions and entitlements of United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) and highlights that the General Principles for the Conduct of Marine Scientific Research set out therein require, *inter alia*, that marine scientific research shall be conducted in compliance with all relevant regulations adopted in conformity with UNCLOS including those for the protection and preservation of the marine environment.
5. OSPAR recognises that marine research scientists appreciate the uniqueness and complexity of the marine environment, and are therefore particularly interested in preserving this scientifically, aesthetically, ecologically, and potentially economically valuable environment. Because of the specialized nature of the equipment required to work in the deep-sea, such as manned and unmanned research submersibles, scientists are the primary group of people who have had the opportunity to visit and value these extraordinary habitats. OSPAR also recognises that scientists have already worked to develop codes of conduct for some deep-sea features, such as hydrothermal vents and cold water corals, and this OSPAR code of conduct has been written to fit harmoniously with those. (Specific provisions concerning the conduct of scientific research in certain deep / high seas habitats will be attached as annexes to this statement as they are developed.)
6. The potential impact of many scientific activities on the marine environment is low in comparison to the potential for disturbance by natural processes (e.g. volcanic/tectonic events, slumps, climate variation, etc.) or other human activities (e.g. mining, fisheries, and shipping). Indeed many areas, especially seamounts and cold coral reefs, have been widely impacted by human activities, like fisheries, long before being scientifically studied. Nonetheless, there remains the possibility that some scientific activities could have unwanted negative

³ For the purposes of this document, *deep sea* shall follow the FAO definition and mean areas of the sea deeper than 200 metres, and *high seas* shall mean the water column and / or the seabed in areas beyond national jurisdiction, within the OSPAR Maritime Area.

side-effects on particular regions or animals if research activities are not carefully planned and executed. In addition, because only a limited number of sites are currently known and scientists from a wide variety of disciplines frequently work at these single locations, there is the potential for conflicting effects among studies, and multiple impacts, particularly at sites where scientific activity is intense.

7. OSPAR recognises that protection and sustainable use of the oceans is best served by a fundamental understanding of its complex marine ecosystems, and that can only be achieved through marine research. OSPAR further recognises that the role of scientists is also of primary importance concerning the implementation of the OSPAR network of Marine Protected Areas, and this should be preceded with the best available science.

8. Thus, marine research is a prerequisite and an integral component of an ecosystem based management of marine resources and the effective conservation of biodiversity of the deep and high seas. Most forms of observation and investigation of natural systems involve some disturbance of the systems being studied. In the interest of environmental stewardship, it must be the goal of research scientists to minimize disturbances as much as possible, while still gathering the information necessary both to understand the systems and to form a basis for sustainable use strategies. Therefore, marine scientists should always evaluate their research plans from a conservative standpoint, and choose the most environmentally friendly research approach.

9. When awarding research grants or research cruise time, the research plans should be assessed against conformity with the following principles.

Conduct of responsible marine science

10. OSPAR requests all scientists working in the deep seas and high seas of the OSPAR maritime area to adhere to the following principles when conducting their work:

- a. **Species:** avoid, in the course of scientific research, activities which could lead to long-lasting changes in regional populations or substantially reduce the number of individuals present.
- b. **Habitats:** avoid, in the course of scientific research, activities which could lead to substantial physical, chemical, biological or geological changes or damage to marine habitats.
- c. **Threatened and/or declining features:** When working in areas of particular ecological vulnerability, including, *inter alia*, the features listed in the OSPAR “List of Threatened and/or Declining Species and Habitats” utmost care should be taken not to disturb or damage the features as far as possible.
- d. **Management areas / marine protected areas:** When working in areas of particular ecological importance and/or sensitivity, including, *inter alia*, OSPAR marine protected areas, care has to be taken not to disturb or damage the protected features, and that activities are in compliance with regulations for the area. Further, scientists are requested to respect the importance of management areas like marine protected areas and are asked to assist in their implementation through the use of the best scientific knowledge.
- e. **Notification and research planning:** Avoid activities which could disturb the experiments and observations of other scientists. This requires that scientists: a) make themselves familiar with the status of current and planned research in an area; and b) that they ensure that their own research activities and plans are known to the rest of the international research community via appropriate public domain data bases and web sites.
- f. **Methods:** Use the most environmentally-friendly and appropriate study methods which are reasonably available.
- g. **Transport of biota:** Ensure that transport of biota between different marine regions, which could lead to changes in the environment or the composition of marine communities, does not occur.
- h. **Collections:** Avoid collections that are not essential to the conduct of the scientific research, and reduce the number of samples to the necessary minimum.

- i. **Collaboration and cooperation:** Ensure the fullest possible use of all biological, chemical and geological samples through collaborations and cooperation within the global community of scientists. Samples which can be archived should be placed in accessible repositories for future use.
 - j. **Data-sharing:** Practise international sharing of data, samples and results in order to minimize the amount of unnecessary sampling and to further a global understanding of the marine environment.
11. OSPAR supports the individual points of this commitment unreservedly and requests all scientists to adhere to them when planning and carrying out their research.
12. Their application should be a prerequisite for the granting of research funds and ship-time.

ARICE2018

CALL FOR SHIP-TIME PROPOSALS

PART B - PROPOSAL TEMPLATE

Project website:

www.arice.eu

Version 10.04.2018

PROPOSAL TEMPLATE

Proposals must be submitted exclusively in electronic form via the [online proposal submission website](#). In order to login, you must first register in the system. Once registered, you will be able to proceed with the proposal submission, which consists of two main parts:

- PART A – General project information and applicant details
- PART B – Scientific project description

This document will guide you to prepare the PART B of the proposal.

Part A – General project information and applicant details

This part consists of the following three menus, containing forms that have to be filled in online:

- General and logistical project information
- Principal Investigator (PI)

In this menu the Principal Investigator has to agree to the following declaration:

I declare that I will observe and carry out any investigation in accordance with the general principles of the „Code of Conduct for Responsible Marine Research in the Deep Seas and High Seas of the OSPAR Maritime Area” (Appendix I), regardless of the area of operation.

I declare that the information provided is accurate and correct. I agree that the ARICE Consortium may make any enquiries it considers necessary to verify the information provided herein. I have read, understand and agree, if successful, to be bound by the Terms and Conditions for funding under the ARICE project as outlined in the Guidelines for Applicants.

- Project partners

Details on how to fill in the PART A of the proposal can be found in the document “ARICE2018 – Online proposal submission guidelines” <https://arice.eu/documents>

PART B – Scientific project description

This part needs to be uploaded as a pdf document at the end of the online application process, following the link “Scientific project description” at the [online proposal submission website](#).

The information provided in this part should not exceed 14 pages. The number of pages’ limit includes appendices, tables and maps, but excludes CVs of the PI and co-proponents for which a dedicated **CV Template** (available at www.arice.eu) has to be used.

The most important parts are the **Scientific Objectives and the Work Programme which should comprise approximately 4 to 5 pages each**. When writing your proposal, keep in mind that the evaluation of the proposal will be based, in large part, on the information provided in this section. The proposal should provide a comprehensive and robust justification for the provision of funding, without referring to cited or additional literature. When writing your proposal you should bear the

ARICE evaluation criteria in mind. The proposal should be as concise as possible to ease the proposal evaluation. A font size of Times New Roman 12pt should be used with 14 pt spacing.

Note for Proposals applying for PRV Polarstern in the MOSAiC expedition ONLY:

The application must also **include an Endorsement Letter from MOSAiC**, which will not count against the page limit. This endorsement is encouraged to be started by potential applicants **as soon as possible**, as the process is expected to take 3 weeks from the submission of the request for endorsement until endorsement is confirmed. Potential applicants should therefore contact the MOSAiC team coordinators (<http://www.mosaic-expedition.org/organisation.html>) as soon as possible to ensure that their project can be embedded in MOSAiC. The MOSAiC Project Board will evaluate the endorsement proposal, possibly consulting with the applicant for more information, and make a decision within 3 weeks. This endorsement letter must be submitted to ARICE together with the ship time proposal. **ARICE will automatically reject proposals lacking the endorsement from MOSAiC.**

The proposal should cover the following sections in the order indicated:

1. Scientific objectives of the proposed work

a) General scientific background

Provide information on the current state of scientific knowledge in the field of research directly linked to the proposed work, including relevant citations. Please describe your own preliminary work in the field.

b) Specific aims of the project

Provide a clear description of the scientific objectives to be achieved with the proposed project highlighting its innovative aspects. What is the expected added value to the present state of knowledge? Provide clear evidence of expected outputs and deliverables from the proposed work and outline clearly the specific benefits and impacts of the research cruise.

Do not exceed **5 pages** for this section.

2. Work programme

Please provide a comprehensive description of the work to be carried out on-board of the icebreaker. This should include a detailed **map of the investigation area**, a **list of stations** (including position and water depths) **and transects**. Outline a realistic timetable and a description of activities in relation to the ship-time requested. This timetable should equally contain distances to be covered and a calculation of time needed to accomplish them at a give cruise speed as well as station time. Please bear in mind that the quality of the work program is central to the evaluation of your proposal and you will therefore need to provide a plausible and conclusive case.

Example:

Activity	Position		Depth / Distance (m)/(nm)	Est. time (h)	Operations
	Latitude (N)	Longitude (W)			
Transit preferred Port of Departure – Station 1	Horta Start: 38.537 End: 37.930	Start: - 28.626 End: -15.820	605nm	60	Underway measurements SST, nutrients
Station 1/Task 1	37.930	-15.820	4283m	2.5	CTD cast
Station 1/Task 2	37.930	-15.820	4283m	3	Multicorer cast
Transect 1	<i>Start:</i> 37.930 <i>End:</i> 35.770	<i>Start:</i> - 15.820 <i>End:</i> -13.180	188nm	30.4	Multichannel seismics line
Etc.					

Total working hours:

Total transit hours:

Do not exceed **5 pages** for this section.

3. IMPACT ON SOCIETY and public outreach

Provide a clear description on how the proposed topic will be able to contribute to societal needs, even in the long run, by i.e. addressing critical issues related to climate change, environment or any other benefit for society. Address whether the proposed research will enhance innovation capacity; create new market opportunities, strengthen competitiveness, if appropriate.

Shortly explain the dissemination activities planned within the project, i.e. to inform the general public about your research cruise and the research that will be performed.

4. Principal investigator, co-proponents and user group

Provide a short description of the Principal Investigator and proposal partners.

Provide information on the number of people joining the on-board team and their assigned tasks (use the table format as in the example below). Please provide details of the expertise/track record of the PI and other partners and participants directly joining the embarked team (including details of ship-based experience). Follow the regulations in terms of affiliations for the teams as stated in the ARICE Eligibility Criteria. Match the expertise of your team in relation to the objectives and work to be carried out. Provide information on the “remote participants” participating on data or sample treatment.

Example:**On board participants**

No	Name	Gender	Affiliation	Early career/in formation*	On-board tasks
.					
1	Fred Flintstone	M	NIOZ, NL	Early career	PI, Sedimentologist
2	NN, Student	F	FMI, FI	In formation	CTD work, Nutrient analysis
	Etc.			No	Seismics watch

Remote participants

No	Name	Gender	Affiliation	Early career/in formation*	Remote participants
.					
1	Laura Sánchez	F	CSIC, SP	Early career	Palinology
2	Marco Rossi , Student	M	CNR, IT	In formation	X Data processing
	Etc.			No	

***Early career:** up to seven years active in science from last degree; **In formation:** PhD/Master student.

Attach brief CVs of **the PI and co-proponents** as appendix (with maximum length of 1 page each), after the main proposal text, using the dedicated CV Template (available at www.arice.eu). The CV collection is the only section which will not count against the proposal page limit. Only the five most recent/important publications should be compiled.

5. Technical capability to carry out the research cruise and data exploitation

Please provide information on the technical equipment necessary to carry out the proposed work and its availability. If applicable, who will benefit from real time data sharing? Give a detailed outline and timeline of how and when gathered data and samples will be analysed, taking into account additional funding sources, since no funding is available within the ARICE project to analyse gathered data and samples. Please describe if applicable if there is “own equipment” or complementary funding available to support the research cruise. Please describe how the knowledge gained through the ARICE funded project will be disseminated and where gained data will be stored.

6. National, International and industrial collaboration

If applicable, please provide information on how your proposed project is embedded into other larger research projects or programs on a national or international level. If applicable, please describe how new user groups with limited access to marine infrastructure will be integrated. If applicable, please provide information on collaboration with industry.

7. Training of young scientists

Please provide information on how you will support the training of young scientists in the frame of your project, pre-, during and/or post-cruise, if you will devote berths to early career researchers/scientists in a training role.

8. Travelling and shipment costs

Please provide a detailed and realistic budget of expenses incurred in relation to travelling of cruise participants and possible shipment of (own) equipment to the preferred port of mobilisation and back from the port of demobilisation. Ports of mobilisation and demobilisation can only be roughly estimated at this stage, as the closest port or the port where the vessel is usually based. The final ports of mobilisation and demobilisation will be fixed by the operators of the ARICE icebreakers at cruise scheduling.

APPLICATION CHECKLIST

HAVE YOU:

- Checked if you satisfy all eligibility criteria?
- Completed every part of the application form?
 - General and logistical information
 - Principal Investigator
 - Project partners
 - Project description
- Finally submitted your proposal?

CLOSING DATE

Proposals must be received online via the [online proposal submission website](#) by

Thursday 5^h of July 2018, 15:00 HOURS (CEST)

The proposal submission website will no longer be accessible after this date. Please allow enough time to upload your proposal to avoid the call closure rush.

Contact Details

ARICE Project Manager

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MEERESFORSCHUNG
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14473 Potsdam, Germany
E-mail: info@arice.eu

CV TEMPLATE

TITLE FULL NAME			
Institution	University/Institute	Phone	Phone number
Affiliation	Faculty	Fax	Fax number
	Department	E-mail	example@awi.de
	Address		
	Country		
Born at	dd/MM/yyyy	Gender	

Degrees + Scientific Career ⁴(please extent/delete as appropriate)

Year/ Periode	
Year/ Periode	
Year/ Periode	
Year	M.Sc.
Year	

Early Career scientist (up to 7 years active in science after last degree)

Years active in science after last degree

Research Topics (please give a brief overview about expertise, appointments, projects, etc., max. 200 words)

Sea-going experience

Relevant Publications (max. 5)

1	
2	
3	
4	
5	

⁴ Including stays abroad
© ARICE Consortium

EVALUATION CRITERIA

Access to any Research Icebreaker in ARICE will be regulated according to the Excellence-driven Access mode. This mode of access is dependent on the scientific excellence, originality, quality and technical and ethical feasibility of an application evaluated through peer review conducted by external experts.

The Scientific Liaison Panel (SLP) will base their selection of scientifically excellent proposals on the external evaluations provided by international experts. Only scientifically excellent-ranked proposals will be considered for the logistical evaluation, ensuring that only excellent proposals are considered for funding.

In case of equally ranked proposals, **priority should be given to user groups composed of users who:**

- have **not previously used the installation**, and
- are **working in countries where no equivalent research infrastructure exist**.

The SPL will apply the principles of transparency, fairness and impartiality.

Collaborative applications from teams and institutions where no equivalent research infrastructure exist, female and young scientists are strongly encouraged. International and/or industrial partners are welcome.

The scientific excellence of proposals complying with the ARICE Eligibility Criteria will be evaluated using the following Evaluation Criteria:

1) Scientific and technical quality of the ship-time proposal (weighting 30%)

a) General scientific background:

Is the current state of knowledge in the research area well described?

Are cited references relevant and reflect the state-of-the-art?

b) Specific aims of the expedition:

Is the proposed topic of high scientific quality and does it provide innovative aspects?

Are the research objectives and expected outputs of the proposal clearly stated? Are they achievable from a scientific point of view?

To which extent do the expected results lead to a progress beyond the current state-of-the-art?

2) Quality of the work programme (weighting 20%)

Is the work plan adequate? Is it clearly described and well defined? Is the research area, the number of planned stations and transects well justified? Can the proposed work plan be realized in the set time?

Are the scheduled tasks and methods adequate to the set objectives? Is it clearly stated which methods and equipment will be employed?

Does the proposed project maximise the use of the research vessel and associated infrastructure? Has the proposal assessed any likely risks and are provisions for downtime/bad weather included?

3) **Impact on society and public outreach (weighting 15%)**

Is the proposed topic able to contribute to societal needs? Would this research enhance innovation capacity; create new market opportunities, strengthen competitiveness, address issues related to climate change or the environment, or bring other important benefits for society?

Are dissemination activities addressing the general public planned?

4) **TECHNICAL CAPABILITY AND Scientific qualification/track record of the proposing PI and user group (weighting 15%)**

a) Technical capability to carry out the research cruise (weighting 5%)

Is all necessary equipment available to carry out the proposed project?

Are there resources available to support the analysis of gathered data and samples?

b) Scientific qualification/track record of the proposing PI and user group (weighting 10%)

Background/track record of the PI related to its active years in science.

Background/track record of the scientific team.

Are the roles and responsibilities of the scientific team clearly stated? Is the combined expertise suitable to achieve the research objectives of the cruise?

5) **Collaboration with international/national partners/industry (weighting 10%)**

To what extent are new user groups with limited access to marine infrastructure integrated?

To what extent is the proposed project embedded into larger research programmes on a national, EU or international level?

What is the potential for a long term integration/collaboration on an international level?

Are collaborations with industry envisaged?

Are there “shore-based scientists” (remote participants) for data treatment and exploitation?
Is a clear concept presented how the gathered data will be shared with shore-based scientists, analysed and published?

6) **Training of early career scientists (weighting 10%)**

Is the training component well defined in the proposal? Is it achievable?

How many early career scientists and students at PhD level and below will be involved?

Are berths devoted to early career researchers/scientists in a training role?

Applicants have to ensure that sufficient information is provided in the proposal to enable a thorough evaluation of all criteria.

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